

Numerical Green's Functions for Rapid Multi-Query Neutron Diffusion Analysis via SVD Compression

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ABSTRACT

This work presents an approach for rapidly evaluating neutron flux distributions under arbitrary source configurations using precomputed numerical Green's functions. Instead of repeatedly solving the diffusion equation for each source distribution, the method computes the system's fundamental response to localized sources once; solutions for arbitrary sources are then reconstructed via superposition. The Green's function matrix, obtained by solving boundary value problems with Gaussian-approximated delta sources, allows immediate flux reconstruction for any imposed source without additional partial differential equation solves. This capability is particularly advantageous for problems involving external sources, such as subcritical reactors driven by accelerators or isotopic sources, shielding calculations with distributed sources, source-detector configurations, and parametric studies requiring numerous evaluations. Verification against analytical solutions in one-dimensional slab geometry shows sub-percent accuracy. Six distinct source distributions (uniform, exponential, Gaussian, localized, asymmetric, and double Gaussian) were used to verify the reconstruction capability. A Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) compression of the Green's function matrix maintains accuracy while reducing computational cost and memory requirements. Only twelve modes are needed to capture 99% of the system's response, whereas twenty-seven modes capture 99.9% with reconstruction errors below 0.3%. The matrix symmetry allows fast adjoint calculations for sensitivity analysis. Extensions to multi-dimensional geometries, time-dependent problems, and transport equations are under development.

Keywords: Green's Functions; Neutron Diffusion; Source Problems; Model Reduction; Singular Value Decomposition

1. INTRODUCTION

Many reactor physics problems, such as subcritical systems driven by accelerators, shielding calculations, and startup simulations, involve external neutron sources rather than self-sustaining criticality. Traditional approaches requiring a new solution for each source configuration become computationally expensive for parameter sweeps and uncertainty quantification. Green's function methods offer an efficient alternative: by computing the system's fundamental response to a point source once, the solution for any arbitrary distribution is constructed through superposition.

Case and colleagues pioneered the systematic use of Green's functions for neutron transport [1], and Vitali et al. further explored adjoint transport formulations relevant to importance and sensitivity calculations [2]. While analytical functions exist only for idealized geometries, numerical computation combined with Model Order Reduction (MOR) offers a path for realistic configurations. Techniques

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like Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) have been successfully applied to compress neutronics solution spaces. German and Ragusa applied POD to diffusion eigenvalues [3], while Buchan et al. developed a POD reduced-order model for eigenvalue problems with application to neutron diffusion and transport [4]. Recently, Phillips et al. applied autoencoders to diffusion problems [5]. In realistic reactor dynamics, Introini et al. demonstrated SVD efficacy for the TRIGA reactor [6], and Riva et al. developed reduced-order techniques for multi-physics bias correction and state estimation [7, 8].

The present work extends these concepts to numerically computed Green's function matrices. Section 2 reviews the mathematical framework and adjoint sensitivity. Section 3 details the numerical computation and analytical verification. Section 4 examines reconstruction accuracy and SVD compression performance, followed by conclusions in Section 5.

2. MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Neutron Diffusion with External Sources

Consider the steady-state, one-dimensional, monoenergetic neutron diffusion equation with an external source, neglecting the extrapolated distance in the vacuum boundary conditions:

$$-D \frac{d^2 \phi(x)}{dx^2} + \Sigma_a \phi(x) = S(x), \quad x \in [-a/2, a/2] \quad (1)$$

subject to vacuum boundary conditions $\phi(\pm a/2) = 0$. Here $\phi(x)$ is the scalar neutron flux, D is the diffusion coefficient, Σ_a is the macroscopic absorption cross section, and $S(x)$ represents an external source distribution.

Defining the diffusion length $L^2 = D/\Sigma_a$:

$$\phi''(x) - \frac{\phi(x)}{L^2} = -\frac{S(x)}{D} \quad (2)$$

This formulation applies to source-driven scenarios in a typical non-multiplying medium.

2.2. Green's Function Solution Framework

The Green's function $G(x, x')$ represents the flux at field point x due to a unit point source at location x' :

$$\frac{d^2 G}{dx^2} - \frac{G(x, x')}{L^2} = -\frac{\delta(x - x')}{D} \quad (3)$$

with $G(\pm a/2, x') = 0$ for all source positions x' .

The key result is that *any* solution to equation (2) can be written as:

$$\phi(x) = \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} G(x, x') S(x') dx' \quad (4)$$

This superposition principle allows immediate flux reconstruction for arbitrary source distributions $S(x)$ without solving equation (2) repeatedly. The Green's function encodes complete system response.

For discrete spatial grids with n field points x_i and m source points x'_j , equation (4) becomes matrix-vector multiplication:

$$\boldsymbol{\phi} = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{s} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ is the Green's function matrix with $G_{ij} \approx G(x_i, x'_j)$ and \mathbf{s} is the discretized source vector.

2.3. Singular Value Decomposition for Compression

The singular value decomposition (SVD) factorizes the Green's function matrix $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ as:

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T = \sum_{k=1}^r \sigma_k \mathbf{u}_k \mathbf{v}_k^T, \quad (6)$$

where $r = \min(n, m)$, the singular values satisfy $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r \geq 0$, and the columns of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are orthonormal.

If the singular values decay rapidly, a rank- K approximation with $K \ll r$ can be obtained by truncating the sum:

$$\mathbf{G}_K = \sum_{k=1}^K \sigma_k \mathbf{u}_k \mathbf{v}_k^T. \quad (7)$$

This low-rank approximation reduces both computational and storage costs. Flux reconstruction using \mathbf{G}_K requires only $O(K(n + m))$ operations, compared to $O(nm)$ for the full matrix. Similarly, the storage requirement decreases from $O(nm)$ to $O(K(n + m))$ entries.

2.4. Adjoint Green's Function and Sensitivity Analysis

For the self-adjoint diffusion operator, the adjoint Green's function satisfies:

$$G^*(x, x') = G(x', x) \quad (8)$$

This provides sensitivity of response functionals to source perturbations. For $R[\phi] = \int w(x)\phi(x)dx$:

$$\frac{\delta R}{\delta S(x')} = \int w(x)G(x, x')dx = \phi^*(x') \quad (9)$$

where $\phi^*(x')$ is the adjoint flux or importance function [9].

3. NUMERICAL METHODS

3.1. Numerical Computation of Green's Functions

The numerical framework employs: domain $x \in [-50, 50]$ cm, diffusion coefficient $D = 0.9$ cm, macroscopic absorption cross section $\Sigma_a = 0.01 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, diffusion length $L \approx 9.49$ cm, spatial discretization with $N = 850$ field points and $M = 101$ source points, and reference source strength $S_0 = 1000 \text{ n}/(\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{s})$.

The Dirac delta is approximated using a narrow Gaussian:

$$\delta_\epsilon(x - x') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\epsilon}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x')^2}{2\epsilon^2}\right) \quad (10)$$

with $\epsilon = 0.01$ cm, small compared to diffusion length L .

For each source position x'_j , the boundary value problem is solved using `scipy.integrate.solve_bvp`. The solution at field point x_i gives matrix element $G_{ij} \approx G(x_i, x'_j)$.

3.2. Verification Against Analytical Solutions

Numerical accuracy is verified through three independent tests:

1. **Boundary conditions:** $|G(\pm a/2, x'_j)| < 10^{-10}$ for all source positions
2. **Uniform source reconstruction:** Comparison with analytical solution
3. **Symmetry verification:** $\max_{i,j} |G_{ij} - G_{ji}| < 10^{-2}$

For a uniform source $S(x) = S_0$, the analytical solution is:

$$\phi(x) = \frac{S_0 L^2}{D} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh(x/L)}{\cosh(a/(2L))} \right) \quad (11)$$

Reconstruction errors are quantified using relative L^2 norm:

$$\varepsilon_{L^2} = \frac{\|\phi_K - \phi_{\text{ref}}\|_2}{\|\phi_{\text{ref}}\|_2} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

3.3. Test Source Distributions

Six source distributions test reconstruction capability across diverse spatial patterns:

Table I. Test source distributions for verification with $S_0 = 1000 \text{ n}/(\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{s})$

Source Type	Mathematical Form
Uniform	$S(x) = S_0$
Exponential	$S(x) = S_0 \exp(-(x + a/2)/\lambda)$, $\lambda = 20 \text{ cm}$
Gaussian	$S(x) = S_0 \exp(-(x/\sigma_G)^2)$, $\sigma_G = a/8$
Localized	$S(x) = S_0$ for $ x < a/8$, $S(x) = 0$ otherwise
Asymmetric	$S(x) = S_0(1 + x/a)$
Double Gaussian	$S(x) = S_0[\exp(-((x - x_1)/\sigma_d)^2) + \exp(-((x - x_2)/\sigma_d)^2)]$, $x_{1,2} = \mp 20 \text{ cm}$, $\sigma_d = 8 \text{ cm}$

These distributions correspond to different physical scenarios: uniform background sources in subcritical assemblies, exponential attenuation profiles from beam sources entering from one side, Gaussian peaks from localized isotopic sources, step functions at material interfaces, asymmetric distributions in shielding geometries, and dual-peak configurations representing multiple discrete source locations.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Verification and Green's Function Computation

Figure 1 compares numerical and analytical Green's functions for three source positions. Maximum absolute difference is 4.4×10^{-3} with maximum relative L^2 error $2.6 \times 10^{-2}\%$ and mean relative L^2 error $4.4 \times 10^{-3}\%$.

Figure 1. Analytical vs numerical Green's functions

Figure 2. Uniform source verification

Figure 2 shows uniform source reconstruction. Numerical integration yields maximum relative error 0.133%. Matrix symmetry is verified with $\max_{i,j} |G_{ij} - G_{ji}| = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$.

4.2. Flux Reconstruction for Arbitrary Sources

The primary capability demonstrated is flux reconstruction for arbitrary imposed sources using equation (5). Table II shows reconstruction accuracy using the full Green's function matrix.

Table II. Flux reconstruction accuracy (full Green's function matrix)

Source	Uniform	Exponential	Gaussian	Localized	Asymmetric	Double Gaussian
L^2 Error (%)	0.059	0.133	0.054	0.066	0.061	0.059

All reconstructions achieve sub-0.14% accuracy, verifying the numerical Green's function approach across diverse source patterns.

Figure 3 shows the full Green's function matrix reconstruction (without SVD compression) for all six source distributions, compared against direct BVP solutions. The close agreement confirms that the numerically computed Green's function matrix accurately encodes the system response for sources with very different spatial characteristics.

Figure 3. Full Green's function matrix reconstruction (no SVD) compared to direct BVP solutions for all six source distributions

4.3. SVD Analysis and Compressed Reconstruction

Figure 4 displays singular value spectrum and cumulative energy. Twelve modes capture 99% of system response, twenty-seven modes reach 99.9%, fifty-seven modes achieve 99.99%.

Figure 5 shows the first six spatial response modes \mathbf{u}_k . The rapid decay reflects smooth diffusion physics where macroscopic transport patterns dominate.

Table III shows reconstruction errors with 27-mode truncated SVD.

Table III. Reconstruction errors with 27 SVD modes

Source	Uniform	Exponential	Gaussian	Localized	Asymmetric	Double Gaussian
Error (%)	0.081	0.287	<0.001	0.164	0.090	<0.001

All sources achieve sub-0.3% error. The exponential source shows the highest error (0.29%) due to its strongly asymmetric character requiring many odd and even modes, while the localized source reaches

Figure 4. Singular value spectrum

Figure 5. First 6 SVD spatial modes

0.16% due to its discontinuous profile. Smooth symmetric sources (Gaussian, double Gaussian) achieve near-machine-precision reconstruction.

Figure 6 shows error decreases monotonically with added modes.

Figure 6. Reconstruction error vs modes

Figure 7. Computational speedup

Figure 8 illustrates the convergence behavior of the SVD reconstruction as the number of retained modes increases. For each source distribution, reconstructions at 5, 10, 20, 27, 50, and 80 modes are overlaid on the same panel together with the reference solution. Smooth, symmetric sources such as the Gaussian and double Gaussian converge rapidly, becoming visually indistinguishable from the reference already at 10 modes. Sources with sharper spatial features or strong asymmetry, such as the localized and exponential distributions, require progressively more modes before the reconstruction converges to the reference.

Figure 7 illustrates the trade-off between computational speedup and reconstruction accuracy as a function of the number of retained SVD modes.

The rapid SVD singular value decay reflects underlying diffusion physics. Macroscopic neutron transport in diffusion-dominated regimes shows inherently low-dimensional structure. The first mode represents symmetric fundamental response. Higher modes encode progressively finer spatial details that contribute negligibly to solutions dominated by diffusion-scale phenomena.

4.4. Adjoint Green's Function for Sensitivity Analysis

Matrix symmetry allows immediate adjoint calculation without additional computational cost. The adjoint Green's function $G^*(x, x') = G(x', x)$ yields sensitivity of any response functional to source perturbations at different locations.

To demonstrate this capability, we consider a detector response at the domain center: $R = \phi(x = 0)$. The sensitivity to source perturbations at any location x' is given by $dR/dS(x') = G(0, x')$, which corresponds to reading a column of the Green's function matrix.

SVD Reconstruction Convergence with Increasing Modes

Figure 8. SVD reconstruction convergence: each panel shows a different source distribution with reconstructions at 5, 10, 20, 27, 50, and 80 modes overlaid on the reference solution

Figure 9 displays both the direct Green's function $G(x, x')$ (flux at field point x due to source at x') and the adjoint $G^*(x, x')$ (importance at x for response at x'). The visual symmetry about the diagonal confirms the self-adjoint property of the diffusion operator, with numerical symmetry error below 10^{-2} .

Figure 10 shows the sensitivity function $dR/dS(x')$ for the center detector response. The peak sensitivity occurs at the center ($x' = 0$), indicating that sources placed at the detector location have maximum impact on the measured flux. The sensitivity decays symmetrically toward the boundaries, following the characteristic diffusion length scale. Sources near the vacuum boundaries ($x' \approx \pm 50$ cm) contribute negligibly to the center response due to neutron absorption and leakage. This importance function can guide optimal source placement in experimental design or identify critical locations for source uncertainties in uncertainty quantification studies.

Figure 9. Direct and adjoint Green's functions

Figure 10. Sensitivity of center flux to source perturbations

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a method for computing Green's functions numerically and reconstructing neutron flux distributions for arbitrary sources. Verification against analytical solutions shows sub-0.14%

accuracy. Six source distributions verified the approach.

SVD compression with twenty-seven modes captures over 99.9% of system response. Reconstruction errors stay below 0.3%. Matrix symmetry provides adjoint Green's functions for sensitivity analysis at no extra cost.

This framework addresses reactor physics problems where the same geometry must be analyzed under many different source distributions. Computing the Green's function matrix once, then reconstructing solutions through matrix-vector multiplication, avoids repeated PDE solves. This is particularly useful for: subcritical reactor systems driven by accelerators where beam parameters vary, shielding calculations evaluating different source positions and intensities, source-detector response analysis optimizing detector placement, and uncertainty quantification campaigns propagating source uncertainties through many perturbation samples. Specific applications include accelerator-driven systems for waste transmutation, reactors with startup sources, and radiation protection calculations.

The technique is being tested with the OpenMC Monte Carlo code. Green's functions are computed via localized source simulations, and the reconstruction is verified against direct transport calculations. Verification of the stationary implementation using the OpenMC neutronics code is ongoing, with applications to multi-dimensional geometries. Furthermore, time-dependent formulations using space-time Green's functions, multi-group energy treatment, and transport equations with angular dependence are planned and currently in progress.

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